

A Web-Based Video Player with an In-Built ASR-Based Subtitle Generator for English Videos

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Abstract—Audio transcription, which bridges the gap between text-based accessibility and spoken communication, is becoming increasingly important in today's digital world. It enhances accessibility for those with hearing impairments, ensures accurate spoken information documentation, and makes audio content easier to find and analyse. For accurate speech-to-text transcription on low-end devices, we present in this work a revised Wav2Vec2-based Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) system trained with the Hugging Face Transformer. The system preprocesses audio by tokenising, normalising, and resampling it into feature vectors. A transformer encoder is then used to process these feature vectors. Frame-level annotations are not required because Connectionist Temporal Classification (CTC) loss is used to associate text sequences with audio attributes. Word Error Rate (WER) evaluation showed that the model performed well, which makes it appropriate for web-based automatic subtitle generation. The system incorporates a web-based video player to improve accessibility and user experience. The subtitles are automatically synchronised and shown when the correct video plays after they have been created and saved. This improves content accessibility for a variety of audiences by guaranteeing that viewers can view accurate subtitles without any delays.

Keywords— Automatic Speech Recognition, Wav2Vec2[3], Transformer, CTC Loss, Hugging Face Trainer, Word Error Rate.

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of transformer-based systems has brought about changes in Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) in recent years [1], [2]. One noteworthy advancement is Facebook's Wav2Vec2[3] approach, which uses self-supervised learning to extract meaningful representations from unprocessed audio data. Wav2Vec2[3] efficiently captures long-range relationships in audio signals using transformer encoders and convolutional layers, allowing for extremely accurate transcription. This method has increased the ASR [1], [2] systems' adaptability and resilience to a broad range of datasets, but it has also increased the systems' limitations.

Although they are not directly viable, the pre-trained Wav2Vec2[3] has been widely used, opening the door for beneficial applications like virtual assistants, transcription services, and automatic subtitle synthesis. To maximise its performance for specific use cases, including managing domain-specific language or noisy settings, this pre-trained model has to be further refined. We provide a system model that enhances Wav2Vec2[3] to achieve high transcription accuracy by utilising sophisticated training strategies, such as dynamic padding, gradient accumulation[12], and mixed precision to guarantee scalability and processing efficiency.

To improve user interaction, the system also incorporates a web-based video player. The subtitles are automatically synchronised and shown when the correct video plays after they have been created and saved. By making it simple to integrate subtitles and improving the efficiency of the speech-to-text system, the video player is essential to providing a user-friendly experience.

In order to create an accessible and scalable solution that can meet the increasing need for accurate and practical speech-to-text transcription, the study focuses on the preprocessing pipeline, training technique, and system assessment for creating an ASR model.

TABLE I
CURRENT AVAILABLE (ASR) MODELS

Model Name	Model Details		
	Provider	(WER)[4], [5]	Languages Supported
Whisper	OpenAI	~10-15%	100+
Google Speech-to-Text	Google	~8-12%	100+
DeepSpeech	Mozilla	~10-20%	English
AssemblyAI	AssemblyAI	~8-10%	English
IBM Watson	IBM	~10-15%	10+

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

An AI-powered auto-subtitle system that compares auto-subtitles, edited subtitles, and no subtitles in educational videos to help Thai secondary school students study[21]. While there was no discernible difference in cognitive burden, the results show that auto-subtitles considerably increase learner comprehension and student satisfaction while performing similarly to human-edited subtitles. But there were drawbacks as well, including inaccurate translations, issues with cognitive load, disparate advantages depending on language ability, and technological constraints.

The foundation of human-computer interaction is speech recognition, which enables the development of mobile assistant applications and accessibility for individuals with disabilities. It facilitates the decoding and recognition of human voice by machines into a variety of formats, including text. The technique known as Automatic Speech Recognition ASR[1] allows for flexible interaction between humans and machine systems, making it easy to use and convenient. It discusses the issues with speech-to-text conversion, including how to handle various dialects, background noise interference, and speech rate. With the aid of sophisticated deep learning models, this method aims to increase ASR[1], [2] accuracy and investigates methods for enhancing transcription accuracy in a noisy setting.

The development of ASR systems has undergone a radical transformation since the advent of PTMs[9], particularly those seen on websites such as Hugging Face. The expenses and knowledge required to develop new ASR applications are significantly decreased by these models, which offer excellent, reusable solutions that may be customised for certain needs utilising headers. To access these models, Hugging Face[9], [10] offered a very user-friendly platform. PTMs were more effective because they made it possible to fine-tune the models on (ASR) tasks more quickly. If a pre-trained model turns out to be less relevant to the domain or language, it may still take a lot of computing power to fine-tune it for a certain task, and the performance may still be less than ideal.

Existent work uses Wav2Vec2[3], a self-supervised learning model for speech recognition-contributes to how this model directly processes audio signals and doesn't require a great volume of labelled data for speech processing. Wav2Vec2[3] further aids in ASR, particularly in situations when labelled data is scarce, by improving speech modelling through a combination of transformers and convolutional layers.

One study on the Transformer[6] variant of deep learning architectures highlights the importance of the Transformer and Attention methods in improving ASR performance, while another examines the long-range dependency management capability for voice data. By focusing on distinct areas of the input speech signal at different times using the attention mechanism[6], the ASR model can manage complex speech patterns and increase transcription accuracy. Transformers' high computing cost, however, is a drawback that prevents them from being used in real-time ASR systems, particularly when processing lengthy speech sequences or functioning in contexts with limited resources.

The study on the application of Transformers[6], [7] and attention scaling in ASR systems gives an account of how scaled dot-product attention improves the attention

mechanism's ability to handle sequential speech data[6].The model performs better when transcribing a variety of speech inputs by adapting the attention mechanism, which makes it more effective at handling speech recognition tasks of different complexity.

In speech analytics, the Word Error Rate[4][5]—a statistic used to evaluate the difference between the anticipated and actual transcriptions—is frequently used to gauge the quality of ASR systems. greater transcription accuracy is indicated by a WER[4], [5]. Interestingly, however, in certain situations, downstream applications may still be successful even if WER is greater than anticipated. Because speech recognition is complicated and interacts with other systems, higher ASR accuracy does not always translate into better overall performance for applications that rely on speech inputs.

III. SYSTEM MODEL

Wav2Vec2[3], a pre-trained transformer-based[6], [7] model, accurately transcribes speech data to text using a CTC [8] loss. It's based on Facebook/Wav2Vec2[3]-base-960h and learns features Abbreviations and Acronyms

1) *Input Processing:*

Data preprocessing guarantees that both audio and text data are in the correct format for the Wav2Vec2[3] model. The first phase is Audio Preprocessing, which filters and resamples raw audio signals up to the target rate of 16 kHz.

This ensures uniformity throughout the dataset and specifies how the model expects inputs. More formally, the original signal $x(t)$ produces a new signal $x'(t)$ by interpolation. This stage removes any possible discrepancies brought on by the dataset's varying sample rates. After resampling, the raw waveforms are normalized to bring all amplitudes inside a predetermined range. In terms of mathematics, the normalization is provided by:

$$x_{norm}(t) = \frac{x(t) - \mu}{\sigma} \quad (1)$$

Where μ is the mean of the signal, σ is the standard deviation, This normalizes the audio so that it has a 0 mean and unit variance.

The Wave2Vec2 is then used to tokenize the normalized waveform audio signals into numerical feature vectors, leveraging convolutional layers that can capture temporal patterns in the waveforms.

Convolutional kernels serve as filters in this technique, capturing localized temporal information that are then supplied into the subsequent transformer layers. At the same time, the audio sample transcriptions are tokenized into integer sequences. An encoded representation of the text aids in sequence alignment during training since the Wave2Vec2 vocabulary assigns a unique ID to each character or word.

2) *Model Architecture: Wav2Vec2 for CTC:*

The three primary components of the transformer-based[6], [7] wav2vec2[3] model, which is tailored for voice recognition applications, are feature extraction, transformer encoding, and sequence prediction with CTC[8] loss. The algorithm computationally extracts high-dimensional information from each frame by processing overlapping audio inputs through convolutional layers.

$$Feature_i = \sum_{k=1}^K w_k \cdot xt + k \quad (2)$$

Where w_k is the weight of the convolution kernel, and k the kernel size. The temporal dimension is compressed while preserving the important patterns found within the audio signal. After that, these features are fed into a transformer encoder, which records the contextual relationships and long-range dependencies between frames. The weighted representation of input information is computed by the transformer with the aid of the self-attention processes. The self-attention mechanism[6][7] is defined as

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V \quad (3)$$

Here in this case, $\sqrt{d_k}$ is the dimensionality of the key vector, while Q, K, and V are the query, key, and value matrices, respectively. This enables the model to dynamically weigh the significance of different frames, capturing global dependencies that are necessary for proper transcription. The next stage is sequence prediction, where a linear classification layer converts the outputs of the transformer [6], [7] to character probabilities. The CTC[8] loss function is used to align the ground-truth transcription y^* with the anticipated sequence y without the need for frame-level annotations. The loss is calculated as follows:

$$L_{CTC} = -\log P(y|x) \quad (4)$$

$P(y|x)$ the conditional probability of the predicted sequence w.r.t input audio. The CTC [8] loss represents the insertions, deletions, and substitutions that can occur, allowing for the flexible alignment between the input and the output sequence.

3) Procedure

- The model is trained using Hugging Face [9], [10]Trainer which streamlines the processes of training larger datasets and complicated models.
- Used several advanced techniques to help speed up the training process.
- In memory-constrained environments, you can use gradient accumulation[12], to simulate larger batch sizes by aggregating gradients over multiple steps. Mixed precision training (fp16)[11] wherever necessary reduces memory requirement and accelerates computation by performing operations on the 16-bit floating-point format. Dynamic padding ensures that it pads each batch to the size of the longest sequence within that batch, eliminating useless processing.
- The training process updates the model parameters to decrease the CTC [8] loss, which in turn helps better align the predicted sequence with the true sequence. Advanced optimizers like AdamW[13] also help increase speed to convergence and reduce overfitting.

4) Post Training Process

After training, the model is assessed and used to transcribe tasks. Token sequences are produced by the Wav2Vec2[3] model after feature vectors extracted from raw audio files are processed by the processor during inference. Using its tokenizer, the processor decodes these tokens back into text. A common statistic in ASR the Word Error Rate (WER) is used by the system to quantify transcribing accuracy.

$$WER = \frac{S+D+I}{N} \quad (5)$$

where N is the total number of words in the ground truth and S, D, and I are the numbers of substitutions, deletions, and insertions, respectively. Its foundation is the Weighted Edit Distance (WER) normalized by the reference length between the reference and forecast transcriptions.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

1) Dataset

The LJSpeech 1.1 dataset, which consists of brief, high-quality audio recordings of a single person reading passages from seven non-fictional books, is appropriate for (ASR)[1], [2] training. The clips range in duration from 1 to 10 seconds. The training set uses half of the 13,100 audio samples, whereas the evaluation uses a small portion. Metadata, including the file path and the transcription text, is attached to every audio sample. To comply with the Wav2Vec2[3] paradigm, all audio files are downsampled to 16 kHz. This rate provides an excellent balance between computational load and audio quality, making it the ideal rate for speech recognition.

Methods such as SpecAugment[14], [15], which enhance model generalisation by introducing synthetic noise, time warping, and frequency masking into the training set, are employed. To give a clear gauge of how well the model performs while generating transcriptions for dependable and unambiguous speech data, the test set is kept unchanged.

2) Pre-training

Fine-tuning a pre-trained Wav2Vec2[3] model ("facebook/Wav2Vec2-base-960h") forms the basis of the experimental setup. This model was pre-trained on 960 hours of tagged speech data, providing a strong basis for domain-specific fine-tuning. To adapt the model to the particular dataset, audio features are extracted and text annotations are tokenised during the pre-training phase.

Learning audio representations from unlabelled audio data is known as pretraining for the Wav2Vec2 model. The model is trained via self-supervised learning, which involves masking parts of the audio and making predictions about masked features. The model can subsequently be improved using labelled data for tasks like voice-to-text by using the rich, context-aware speech patterns that are learnt throughout this process.

TABLE II.
COMPARISON OF ASR MODELS

Model Name	Model Details		
	Dataset	(WER)	Languages Supported
facebook/Wav2Vec2[3]-base	Librispeech	~5-10%	English
facebook/Wav2Vec2[3]-base-960h	Librispeech	~3.0-4.0%	English
facebook/Wav2Vec2[3]-large-960h	Librispeech	~2.0-3.0%	English
facebook/Wav2Vec2[3]-large-xlsr-53	XLSR (53 languages)	~5-15%	Multilingual

3) Fine Tuning

After pre-training, the Wav2Vec2[3] model is then fine-tuned to output character sequences from audio input in an end-to-end training system (via Connectionist Temporal Classification (CTC) [8] loss) which is appropriate for this kind of task (speech recognition), where a learning model has to perform a joint alignment between the frames from the acoustic space and the output text, without the necessity of having an explicit frame-level annotation.

The Fine-Tuning process is controlled by a few key hyperparameters:

- **Batch Size:** Limited to 2 samples per device, gradients are accumulated over 4 steps due to hardware constraints.
- **Learning Rate:** Selected a Learning Rate $3e - 4$ [16], [17], allowing the model to converge quickly.
- **Epochs:** To prevent overfitting while ensuring the model is adequately exposed to the training data, it is trained for 5 epochs.
- **Hardware:** To optimize memory usage and computation speed on low-end systems, mixed-precision training (FP16) [11] is employed.

Fig. 1. Proposed (ASR)[1], [2] Model for Audio Transcription Task

In order to improve the robustness of the model, SpecAugment [14], [15] applies time warping, frequency masking, and time masking to the audio characteristics. This data augmentation technique is utilised in the fine-tuning process to prevent overfitting and increase diversity in input audio features.

Mixed-precision (FP16) [11] is used in the training procedure while preserving computational accuracy. By matching input sequences with the longest sequence in each batch, dynamic padding guarantees effective use of GPU resources. By simulating larger batch sizes, gradient accumulation[12] allows for reliable training even on memory-constrained platforms.

4) Inference and Subtitle Generation

The audio is pre-processed, and then it is passed to the fine-tuned ASR model for transcription generation. The audio from the given video is initially extracted using tools like librosa and libraries like MoviePy to ensure a constant sampling rate (e.g., 16 kHz)[18]. The self-trained ASR model transforms the audio waveform into text by converting logits into anticipated tokens with the help of a tokenizer and pre-trained parameters. The transcription is divided into segments based on the length of the audio, and each token is assigned an approximate timestamp.

The SubRip Subtitle (SRT) standard is followed in preparing each segment, ensuring linguistic and temporal integrity while accurately synchronizing with the audio sequence. To enhance compatibility with the web-based video player, the generated SRT subtitles are converted into WebVTT (VTT) format, allowing for improved styling, positioning, and interactive features..

5) Potential Deployment

The system incorporates a web-based video player to enhance usability and accessibility. After generation, the subtitles are converted to VTT format, automatically synchronized, and displayed when the corresponding video is played. This ensures seamless subtitle integration, allowing users to engage with the content effectively.

The backend is implemented using Flask, which efficiently handles video and subtitle processing, while the frontend is built with React to provide an interactive and dynamic user interface. The React Player library is used in the frontend to allow users to upload and play videos directly within the application. This enables a smooth experience, as users can upload a video, process it through the wav2vec2 ASR system, and view it with generated subtitles.

Fig. 2. Model for Web Video Video Player

V. RESULT

The evaluation metric used is (WER)[4], [5], a widely accepted statistic for assessing speech recognition accuracy by considering insertions, deletions, and substitutions between the reference text and the model's transcribed output. To analyze the accuracy of the Fine-Tuned Wav2Vec2model, we compared it with OpenAI's Whisper[19]. For the given audio samples, both models produced approximately similar WER results, indicating that transcription errors in both are minimal relative to the reference (ground truth)text.

Both models had similar difficulties in transcribing the audio files when comparing the predicted text to the reference text of the test dataset. For instance, one audio sample might have background noise or complicated phrases that made it more difficult for both algorithms to predict the words correctly. In these situations, Wav2Vec2[3] and Whisper[19] both committed comparable mistakes in terms of deletions and substitutions.

Fig. 3. WER, Heat Map of Whisper[19] and Wav2Vec2[3] Model

TABLE III.
COMPARISON OF THE RESULT FROM THE WHISPER MODEL AND WAV2VEC2 MODEL

Original Transcription	Predicted Transcription	
	Whisper	Wav2Vec2
For although the Chinese took impressions from wood blocks.	For although the Chinese took impressions from wood blocks.	for although the Chinese took impressions from wood blocks.
than in the same operations with ugly ones.	then in the same operations with ugly ones.	an in the same operations with ugly ones.

The frontend of this project was developed using React with CSS and SCSS to ensure a seamless and visually appealing user experience. The interface was designed to allow users to upload video files, track progress, and download generated subtitles in SRT and VTT formats. The backend, built using Flask, handled file processing, audio extraction, ASR transcription, and subtitle generation. The Wav2Vec2 model processed raw speech data. Flask routes managed requests efficiently, ensuring smooth interaction between the frontend and backend. A progress tracking system was implemented to update users in real time. The final subtitles were formatted and stored for download, enhancing accessibility. This integration provided a robust, offline-ready solution for automated subtitle generation.

VI. CONCLUSION

Whisper[19] and Wav2Vec2[3] demonstrated similar (WER)[4], [5], proving their effectiveness for brief audio transcription and establishing their suitability for various real-world applications. Their comparable performance enables their use in voice assistants, automatic video captioning, and meeting transcription, benefiting industries such as media, customer service, healthcare, and education. Additionally, integrating the transcription system with a web-based video player enhances accessibility, ensuring synchronized subtitle display during playback. The React frontend provides a user-friendly interface for video uploads and progress tracking, while the Flask backend efficiently handles file processing, ASR transcription, and subtitle generation. This robust and scalable system offers a reliable

solution for automated captioning, making it valuable for educational platforms, content creation, and multimedia accessibility.

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